

Analysis and Experimentation of Polypropylene Fibre Reinforced Self Compacting Concrete with Replacement of River Sand

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Abstract— Fine aggregate is a vital constituent of concrete, and the excessive use of natural river sand has led to serious environmental concerns, necessitating the use of sustainable alternatives such as quarry dust. This study investigates the performance of self-compacting polypropylene fibre reinforced concrete incorporating quarry dust as partial replacement of river sand, along with fly ash and silica fume as supplementary cementitious materials. Various SCC mixes were prepared and evaluated for filling ability, passing ability, and segregation resistance as per EFNARC guidelines. Results show that all mixes satisfied the workability requirements, although quarry dust mixes exhibited relatively lower flowability due to higher fines content. Fly ash improved workability, while silica fume reduced it because of its high specific surface area. Optimum replacement levels were identified as 30% fly ash or 5% silica fume for quarry dust mixes and 20% fly ash or 15% silica fume for river sand mixes to achieve maximum strength. Quarry dust–fly ash blends achieved the highest compressive strength of 58 MPa and exhibited superior durability with low sorptivity. Structural beam tests demonstrated improved load-carrying capacity of SCC mixes compared to conventional concrete, with polypropylene fibres enhancing ultimate load performance. Finite element analysis and predictive modeling showed close agreement with experimental results, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Keywords— *Self-compacting concrete, Quarry dust, Polypropylene fibre, Fly ash, Silica fume, Durability.*

I. Introduction

Concrete is the most widely used construction material in the world due to its versatility, strength, and durability. Among its constituents, fine aggregate plays a critical role in governing the workability, strength, and long-term performance of concrete. Traditionally, natural river sand has been extensively used as fine aggregate because of its suitable grading, rounded particle shape, and favorable bonding characteristics[1]. However, rapid urbanization and large-scale infrastructure development have led to excessive extraction of river sand, resulting in severe environmental issues such as riverbed degradation, groundwater depletion, ecological imbalance, and social conflicts. These concerns have compelled researchers and engineers to explore sustainable, eco-friendly, and economically viable alternatives to natural river sand for concrete production[2].

Self-compacting concrete (SCC) is an advanced form of concrete that can flow under its own weight, completely fill the formwork, and pass through congested reinforcement without the need for mechanical vibration. SCC offers significant advantages, including improved surface finish, reduced labor requirements, minimized noise pollution, and enhanced structural integrity[3]. However, achieving the desired fresh and hardened properties of SCC requires careful selection and proportioning of materials, especially fine aggregates and mineral admixtures. The use of alternative fine aggregates in SCC must therefore be thoroughly investigated to ensure that workability, strength, and durability requirements are satisfied[4].

Quarry dust, a byproduct obtained during the crushing of stones in quarries, has emerged as a potential substitute for river sand. Large quantities of quarry dust are generated every year, and its disposal poses serious environmental and land-use problems[5]. Utilizing quarry dust as fine aggregate in concrete not only addresses waste management issues but also conserves natural sand resources and

promotes sustainable construction practices. However, quarry dust contains a higher proportion of fines and angular particles compared to river sand, which can significantly influence the rheological behavior and mechanical performance of SCC[6]. Hence, understanding its effect on SCC properties is essential before recommending its widespread application.

The incorporation of supplementary cementitious materials such as fly ash and silica fume further enhances the sustainability and performance of concrete[7]. Fly ash, a byproduct of thermal power plants, improves workability due to its spherical particle shape and contributes to long-term strength and durability through pozzolanic reactions. Silica fume, on the other hand, is an ultra-fine material that significantly refines the pore structure of concrete, leading to higher strength and improved resistance to aggressive environments, although it may reduce workability if not properly managed. Binary and ternary blending of these materials with cement has been proven effective in optimizing both fresh and hardened properties of SCC[8].

Polypropylene fibres are commonly used in concrete to control plastic shrinkage cracking, enhance tensile and flexural performance, and improve post-cracking behavior. In self-compacting concrete, the addition of fibres must be carefully balanced to avoid adverse effects on flowability and passing ability. When properly incorporated, polypropylene fibres can significantly improve the crack resistance, toughness, and structural performance of SCC elements without compromising durability[9].

In addition to mechanical properties, durability is a key factor governing the service life of concrete structures. Parameters such as sorptivity, chloride penetration resistance, sulphate resistance, and acid resistance are particularly important for SCC used in aggressive environmental conditions. Evaluating these durability aspects for quarry dust-based SCC is necessary to establish its suitability for long-term structural applications.

Furthermore, assessing the structural behavior of SCC beams provides practical insight into load-carrying capacity, deflection characteristics, ductility, and failure modes [10].

With advancements in computational tools, finite element analysis has become a powerful method for simulating the structural response of concrete elements and visualizing crack patterns and failure mechanisms. Similarly, data-driven approaches such as artificial neural networks and regression models offer effective means for predicting concrete performance parameters based on experimental data. Integrating experimental, numerical, and predictive modeling approaches enhances the reliability and applicability of research outcomes.

The present study focuses on the analysis and experimentation of self-compacting polypropylene fibre reinforced concrete using quarry dust as fine aggregate, along with fly ash and silica fume as mineral admixtures. The study aims to evaluate fresh, mechanical, durability, and structural properties, identify optimum material proportions, and validate experimental findings using numerical and predictive models. This comprehensive approach contributes to the development of sustainable, high-performance SCC and promotes the effective utilization of industrial byproducts in modern construction.

II. Material and Method

This study investigates the performance of self-compacting polypropylene fibre reinforced concrete incorporating quarry dust as fine aggregate. The materials used include ordinary Portland cement, fly ash, silica fume, river sand, quarry dust, coarse aggregate, potable water, polypropylene fibres, and a polycarboxylate ether-based superplasticizer. The chapter presents the characterization of all constituent materials, mix proportioning, preparation of test specimens, and experimental procedures adopted to evaluate fresh, mechanical, durability, and structural properties. In addition, numerical modeling using finite element analysis and predictive modeling using artificial neural networks and regression techniques were also employed.

Cement: Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of 53 grade conforming to IS: 12269-1987 was used throughout the experimental program. The physical and mechanical properties of cement were determined as per IS: 4031-1988, including standard consistency, setting time, compressive strength, and specific gravity. The cement exhibited adequate early and later-age strength, making it suitable for producing high-performance self-compacting concrete mixes.

Fly Ash: Class F fly ash obtained from the Ennore Thermal Power Plant, Chennai, was used as a supplementary cementitious material. Fly ash collected from electrostatic precipitators is a finely divided residue with low calcium content, enhancing the workability and long-term performance of concrete. The fly ash had a specific gravity of 2.27 and its chemical composition confirmed high silica and alumina content, indicating good pozzolanic reactivity suitable for SCC applications.

Silica Fume: Silica fume, also known as condensed silica fume, was used as a mineral admixture to enhance strength and durability. Due to its extremely fine particle size and high specific surface area, silica fume significantly refines the pore structure of concrete through pozzolanic and

filler effects. Its physical and chemical properties indicate high silica content, contributing to improved early strength, reduced permeability, and enhanced resistance to aggressive environments.

Fine Aggregates: Natural river sand conforming to IS: 383-1970 was used as the conventional fine aggregate, while quarry dust obtained from local stone crushing units was used as a partial replacement. Both materials were tested in accordance with IS: 2386-1963. River sand belonged to grading zone II and exhibited good workability characteristics, whereas quarry dust belonged to grading zone III and contained higher fines, which influenced the rheological behavior of SCC mixes.

Coarse Aggregate: Locally available crushed coarse aggregate with a maximum nominal size of 12.5 mm was used in this study. The aggregate satisfied the grading requirements of IS: 383-1970 and was tested as per IS: 2386-1963. The physical and mechanical properties, such as specific gravity, bulk density, water absorption, impact value, and crushing value, indicated good strength and suitability for SCC production.

Chemical Admixture: A modified polycarboxylate ether-based superplasticizer with viscosity-modifying properties was used to achieve the required flowability and stability of SCC. The admixture enhanced workability without increasing water content and minimized segregation and bleeding. The selected superplasticizer, supplied by Don Chemicals Ltd., provided high water reduction, improved cohesion, and better pumpability of the concrete mixes.

Polypropylene Fibres and Methodology:

Polypropylene fibres with a diameter of 0.5 mm were incorporated to improve crack resistance, ductility, and energy absorption capacity of SCC. The fibres were uniformly dispersed during mixing to avoid balling. Concrete mixes were prepared as per ENARC guidelines, and specimens were cast and cured under standard conditions. Fresh properties were evaluated using slump flow, V-funnel, and L-box tests, while hardened properties, durability, and structural performance were experimentally studied. Finite element modeling using ANSYS and predictive modeling using ANN and regression analysis were conducted to validate and correlate the experimental findings.

In this work, the mix codes are used to understand the mix composition. The capital letters in the mix code such as FA and SF designates fly ash and silica fume respectively. Also, suffix numeral indicates the amount of mineral admixtures in the mix. Further, the letter RS, QD and PPF in the mix represent river sand, quarry dust and polypropylene fibre respectively. Moreover, mix code with letter CM is taken as control mix. The design combination was created by following ENARC's requirements. To create a M 30 grade SCC mix, a number of experiments were conducted using different amounts of fly ash, silica fume, coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, and super plasticizer. According to the literature that is currently available, 0.1% polypropylene fiber was employed in this work. Table 3.10 and Table 3.11, respectively, provide information on SCC mixes that contain river sand and quarry dust as fine aggregate. Only SCC mixtures with 100% quarry dust as a fine aggregate were used in the durability tests.

Figure 1: Split Tensile Strength Testing

Figure 2: Flexural Strength Testing

Figure 3: Testing Input Data

Figure 4: Results for Training and Testing Input

Figure 5: Schematic Diagram of Regression model

It is necessary to use basic form of the equation with a number of regression coefficients to carry out Regression analysis. The experimental data was used to calibrate the values of unknown regression coefficients. Sufficient care was taken to ensure that differences between experimental data and predicted values are minimum. The parameters such as loads and deflection at various stages, ductility, energy absorption and energy ductility are considered as independent parameters. The various constituents of concrete such as the fly ash, silica fume, polypropylene fiber, sand, quarry dust, fck and steel percentage in concrete are named as dependent parameters. These parameters are known after the prediction. Therefore, the regression is a process of predicting dependent parameters using known independent parameters. In the present work, Original program software was used to develop the regression model.

III. Results and Discussion

This section presents the parameters of fresh SCC constructed using 100% quarry dust as fine aggregate (SSC-QD) and river sand as fine aggregate (SSC-RS). The strength characteristics of SCC-RS and SSC-QD binary and ternary blended concrete are also covered in this chapter. This chapter also discusses the durability of SSC-QD binary and ternary blended concrete. Moreover, structural performance fibre reinforced SCC-QD and SCC-RS binary as well as ternary blended concrete is incorporated in this chapter. Finally, the simulation of behavior of experimental beam, modeling with Artificial Neural Network and regression modeling are also included.

Table 1: Compressive Strength of SCC- RS Blended Concrete

S. No	Mix code	Compressive Strength (MPa)		
		3 days	7 days	28days
1	CM (RS)	18	35	40
2	RS-FA10	22	36	43.2
3	RS-FA20	25	38	45.5
4	RS-FA30	17	34	42.6
5	RS-SF5	24	37	43.2
6	RS-SF10	26	39	46.3
7	RS-SF15	27	42	52.2
8	RS-SF20	16	32	36.8
9	RS-SF5-FA30	18	28	34
10	RS-SF10-FA20	21	36	44.5
11	RS-SF15-FA10	23	37	48.2

Figure 6: Compressive Strength of SCC-RS Blended Mixes

Figure 7: Crack Pattern in SCC Beam Representing QD-FA10-SF15-PPF Mix

Figure 8: Root Mean Square Error for GRNN Predictions

Every SCC combination satisfies the EFNARC workability requirements. Additionally, compared to SCC-QD mixtures, all SCC-RS blended mixes have demonstrated comparatively greater workability. The workability of SCC-QD mixes decreased with the amount of particles in the quarry dust. Furthermore, compared to control mixes, the SCC-FA binary blended and SCC-FA-SF ternary blends have shown improved workability. A higher FA concentration also improved the mixtures' workability because of their spherical form and low specific surface area. However, compared to control mixes and SCC-FA mixes, SCC-SF binary blended mixes produced comparatively less workability. The concrete was less workable due to the extremely high specific surface area of SF.

The kind of fine aggregate used in concrete determines the ideal amount of cement replacement with mineral additives to provide optimal compressive strength. It is clear that the best ratio to substitute for cement in SCC-RS mixtures to provide them maximal strength is 20% FA or 15% SF. The ideal ratio to substitute for cement in SCC-QD mixtures, however, is 30% FA or 5% SF to provide the concrete its maximum strength. With a strength of 58 MPa, the QD-FA30 mix outperformed the RS-SF15 mix among the binary blended SCC. The QD-SF15-FA10 mix produced a maximum strength of 50 MPa in the case of ternary blended mixes, which is comparatively lower than that of binary blended mixes. Although it produced a maximum strength of 50 MPa, the QD-SF15-FA10 mix was comparatively weaker than binary blended mixtures. The trend of SCC's tensile and flexural strength fluctuations is nearly identical to that of its compressive strength.

All SCC-QD mixes exhibited relatively low sorptivity than control mix. Also, among all the SCC-QD mixes, binary blended SCC-QD-SF mixes have demonstrated relatively low sorptivity followed by ternary blended SCC – QD and binary blended SCC-QD-FA. The QD-SF20 binary blended SCC has shown the least sorptivity. Further, all the SCC-QD mixes have demonstrated relatively better durability than control mix. Moreover, among all SCC-QD mixes, the binary blended SCC-QD-SF mixes have demonstrated relatively higher durability, followed by ternary blended SCC

– QD and binary blended SCC-QD-FA. The QD-SF20 binary blended SCC has shown very high durability. The load at first crack and deflection of beams representing SCC-QD and SCC-RS mixes are significantly higher than the Conventional control beam. Also, the beams representing SCC-SF binary blended mixes have demonstrated highest load at first crack as well as deflection than the beams representing SCC-FA binary blend and mixes with out mineral admixtures. Further, all the beams representing SCC-QD mixes have demonstrated relatively higher load and deflection at first crack than SCC-RS mixes. Similar observations have been made even in the case of yield load and deflection.

Further, the beams representing SCC-RS and SCC-QD mixes have demonstrated significantly greater ultimate load and deflection than control. Also, the beams made of SCC-QD mixes have exhibited marginally superior ultimate load and deflection than SCC-RS mixes. In addition, the blended mixes have yielded remarkably greater ultimate load and deflection than non-blended mixes. Moreover, the beams representing SCC-FA mixes have shown the remarkably higher ultimate load than SCC-SF mixes but not deflection. Further, the beams made of ternary blended mix with PPF have exhibited highest ultimate strength among all mixes. However, these mixes have not shown higher deflection at ultimate load. The highest deflection of 18.25mm was recorded by QD-SF mix.

Moreover, the beams representing SCC-RS and SCC-QD mixes have shown remarkably higher ductility and energy ductility and energy absorption than the Conventional concrete beams. Also, the beams representing SCC-SF binary blended mixes have demonstrated highest ductility and it is followed by ternary blended SCC, SCC-FA and non-blended mixes. However, ternary blended SCC has exhibited highest energy ductility as well as energy absorption and it is followed by SCC-FA,

SCC-SF and non-blended mixes. Further, all the beams representing SCC-QD mixes have demonstrated relatively higher ductility than SCC-RS mixes.

The three-dimensional finite element approach used to simulate the concrete beams turned out to be a dependable forecasting tool for concrete beam analysis. However, it is very crucial to pick appropriate finite elements and right mesh density to achieve adequate solution to the issue, while carrying out non-linear finite element analysis. Additionally, it has been discovered that the structural performance features of FRSCC may be reasonably predicted using multivariate linear regression. The experimental and projected outcomes have been found to be in close agreement.

IV. Conclusion

The present study concludes that all SCC mixes satisfied EFNARC workability requirements, with river sand mixes showing higher workability than quarry dust mixes due to lower fines content. Fly ash significantly improved workability, whereas silica fume reduced it because of its high specific surface area. Optimum cement replacement levels were identified as 20% fly ash or 15% silica fume for SCC-RS mixes and 30% fly ash or 5% silica fume for SCC-QD mixes to achieve maximum strength. Among binary blends, the SCC-QD-FA30 mix achieved the highest compressive strength of 58 MPa, while ternary blends

showed slightly lower strength but balanced performance. Quarry dust-based SCC mixes exhibited lower sorptivity and superior resistance to chloride, sulphate, and acid attack compared to control concrete, indicating enhanced durability. SCC-QD-SF mixes demonstrated the best durability performance due to a denser microstructure. Structural beam tests revealed significantly higher first crack, yield, and ultimate loads for SCC beams compared to control beams. The incorporation of polypropylene fibres markedly improved ultimate load capacity and ductility. Finite element analysis results closely matched experimental behavior, validating the modeling approach. Predictive models using GRNN and multivariate regression showed good agreement with experimental results. Overall, quarry dust is confirmed as an effective and sustainable fine aggregate for improving the performance of self-compacting concrete.

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